

Green synthesis of thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinones

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Abstract : Reaction of 1,4-naphthoquinones adsorbed on neutral alumina to thiophenols in ambient conditions gave respective mono thiophenyl 1,4-naphthoquinones regioselectively in quantitative yield. The solvent free synthesis and quantitative conversion makes the process practical method.

Keywords : Naphthoquinone, alumina, thiophenol, quinonoid.

Introduction

Now a days there is an increasing interest on the use of environmental benign reagents and procedures to access library of organic compounds. The absence of solvents coupled with the high yields and short reaction times makes these procedures very attractive for synthesis. The drive for the development of dry media reactions in chemistry is due to (a) their economics as it saves money on solvents, (b) ease of purification as solvent is not required to remove after synthesis, (c) high reaction rate and (d) environmental friendly nature as solvent is not required¹⁻⁴.

Thioarylquinones are known to possess fungicidal⁵, antitumor⁶ and antibacterial^{7,8} properties. Quinones are particularly important in dye chemistry and are commercially available. Thioquinone type dye stuffs got attention in search for new infrared dyes for optical recording media⁹. Recently thioarylated quinones have been utilized effectively for the synthesis of various naturally occurring naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-diones¹⁰. Thiophenylation is also a well known tool for protection and deprotection of a functional group¹¹. Several reagents are known for thioarylation in literature such as thiols with phenylsulfenyl chloride¹², thiophenols with nitro

olefins¹³, thiols with KF/alumina², aniline and thiophenols¹⁴. In the past thioaryl-1,4-quinones have been prepared by the addition of thiol to 1,4-quinones in methanol and oxidation of the resulting substituted hydroquinone by an oxidizing agent¹⁵. Recently, a green synthesis of thioaryl-1,4-quinones by Michael addition of thiols to 1,4-quinones in water was also reported¹⁶. But all these procedures have drawbacks of low product yields and longer reaction periods.

Results and discussion

This communication deals with the concept of utilizing reactants adsorbed on an insoluble inorganic support for organic synthesis. For this several classes of solids have been reported including aluminas, silica gels, zeolites and clays. Alumina is available in three forms : (i) basic alumina, (ii) acidic alumina and (iii) neutral alumina. It is important to ensure that the correct type of alumina is employed because of catalytically induced reactions which each may cause with particular functional compounds. The activity of all the three forms of alumina, which is broadly regarded as relating both to the magnitude of the attractive forces between the surface groups on the absorbent and the molecules being absorbed and to the number of sites at which such attractions take

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place³. In the present study an attempt was made to improve upon the yields by carrying out direct thiophenylation of 1,4-naphthoquinones adsorbed on alumina with thiophenol. This procedure has the distinct advantage as thiophenylation proceed quantitatively under mild conditions at active quinonoid positions under solvent-free conditions with no side reactions. The tentative reaction mechanism is shown in Scheme 2. The surface hydroxyl groups of neutral alumina helps in the reaction as shown in the schematic diagram.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Products are characterized by physical and spectral data. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer (values in cm^{-1}). NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer (90 MHz). Yields refer to isolated pure products.

General procedure :

1,4-Naphthoquinone (**1**; 1 mmol, 158 mg) was adsorbed on neutral alumina by dissolving it in acetone, adding the alumina and evaporating the solvent using a rotatory evaporator. To the alumina containing the adsorbed quinone, thiophenol (1.1 mmol, 0.2 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for half an hour. The progress of the reaction was monitored on a TLC plate (silica gel, benzene). After the completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was extracted with acetone. Acetone was evaporated under reduced pressure, the residue thus obtained was separated by preparative TLC over silica gel using petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) as a solvent to give yellow prisms (R_f 0.79, yield 240 mg), m.p. 158 °C. It was identified as 2-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**11**) by its spectral data and melting point. Similarly, other 1,4-naphthoquinones (**2-10**) on reaction gave corresponding thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinones (**12-18**) (Scheme 1).

Spectral data :

2-Thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**11**) : NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 6.20 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 7.50–7.65 (5H, m, $\text{C}_2\text{-SPh}$), 7.70–7.90 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{6,7}\text{-H's}$), 8.00–8.30 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{5,8}\text{-H's}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 1660, 1640 cm^{-1} .

2-Methyl-3-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**12**) : NMR

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1 R = R ¹ = R ² = H | 11 R = R ¹ = R ² = H |
| 2 R = CH ₃ , R ¹ = R ² = H | 12 R = CH ₃ , R ¹ = R ² = H |
| 3 R = Cl, R ¹ = R ² = H | 13 R = Cl, R ¹ = R ² = H |
| 4 R = OH, R ¹ = R ² = H | 14 R = OH, R ¹ = R ² = H |
| 5 R = Br, R ¹ = R ² = H | 15 R = Br, R ¹ = R ² = H |
| 6 R = NH ₂ , R ¹ = R ² = H | 16 R = NH ₂ , R ¹ = R ² = H |
| 7 R ¹ = OH, R = R ² = H | 17 R ¹ = OH, R = R ² = H |
| 8 R = Br, R ¹ = OH, R ² = H | 18 R ² = CH ₃ , R = R ¹ = H |
| 9 R ² = CH ₃ , R = R ¹ = H | |
| 10 R = Cl, R ¹ = H, R ² = CH ₃ | |

Scheme 1

Table 1. Thiarylation of quinones

Reactant	Product ^a	Time (h)	Yield ^b (%)	m.p. (°C)
1	11	0.5	90	158 ¹⁵
2	12	1.0	80	109 ¹⁵
3	13	0.5	90	104 ¹⁵
4	14	8.0	75	149 ¹⁷
5	15	0.5	90	132 ¹⁸
6	16	4.0	85	171 ⁷
7	17	0.5	70	143 ¹⁹
8	17	0.5	65	143 ²⁰
9	18	1.0	75	167 ²⁰
10	18	0.5	70	167 ²⁰

^aProducts are characterized by physical and spectral data.

^bYields refer to isolated pure products.

(CDCl_3) δ : 2.40 (3H, s, $\text{C}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 7.20–7.50 (5H, m, $\text{C}_3\text{-SPh}$), 7.60–7.90 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{6,7}\text{-H's}$), 8.00–8.30 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{5,8}\text{-H's}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 1655, 1640 cm^{-1} .

2-Chloro-3-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**13**) : NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.30–7.50 (5H, m, $\text{C}_3\text{-SPh}$), 7.60–7.80 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{6,7}\text{-H's}$), 7.90–8.10 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{5,8}\text{-H's}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 1675, 1660 cm^{-1} .

2-Hydroxy-3-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**14**) : NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.35–7.55 (5H, m, $\text{C}_3\text{-SPh}$), 7.60–7.80 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{6,7}\text{-H's}$), 7.90–8.10 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{5,8}\text{-H's}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 3450, 1675, 1660 cm^{-1} .

2-Bromo-3-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**15**) : NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.40–7.60 (5H, m, $\text{C}_3\text{-SPh}$), 7.65–7.85 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{6,7}\text{-H}'\text{s}$), 7.90–8.10 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{5,8}\text{-H}'\text{s}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 1680, 1640 cm^{-1} .

2-Amino-3-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**16**) : NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 5.60–5.90 (2H, br, s, $\text{C}_2\text{-NH}_2$), 6.80–7.10 (5H, m, $\text{C}_3\text{-SPh}$), 7.30–7.60 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{6,7}\text{-H}'\text{s}$), 7.70–8.00 (2H, m, $\text{C}_{5,8}\text{-H}'\text{s}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 3400, 1680, 1645 cm^{-1} .

5-Hydroxy-2-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**17**) : NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 5.98 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 6.70–7.10 (5H, m, $\text{C}_2\text{-SPh}$), 7.20–7.60 (3H, m, $\text{C}_{6,7,8}\text{-H}'\text{s}$), 12.02 (1H, s, $\text{C}_5\text{-OH}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 3500, 1660, 1640 cm^{-1} .

6-Methyl-2-thiophenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (**18**) : NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 2.60 (3H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_3$), 7.00 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 7.20–7.60 (5H, m, $\text{C}_2\text{-SPh}$), 7.90 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$), 8.20 (1H, s, $\text{C}_5\text{-H}$), 8.39 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, $\text{C}_8\text{-H}$); IR (nujol) ν_{max} : 1660, 1640 cm^{-1} .

Conclusions :

Neutral alumina was used as catalyst for thiophenylation to achieve regioselectivity with substantial enhancement in yields of thiophenyl quinones. The experimental results clearly showed that the alumina catalyzed method significantly improved both regioselectivity and yields. Naphthoquinones are thiophenylated by neutral alumina at room temperature stirring with thiophenol in good to excellent yields. In addition, this procedure provides quantitatively good yields under mild solvent-free conditions with no side reactions. Moreover, the catalyst can be regenerated and used again. Hence it can be concluded that reaction offers an alternative better method for preparation of thiophenylated naphthoquinones and can be extended to other compounds as well.

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